

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
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DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL TV SERVICES IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITALIZATION OF THE ECONOMY

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Abstract: In this article discusses the development of digital TV services in the conditions of digitalization of the economy. Described the processes of digital television's entry into the field of information transmission, its development, and its advantages and disadvantages compared to other systems.

Key words: digital technologies, digital television, television broadcasting, radio spectrum, interactive services, digital broadcasting.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish sharoitida raqamli televideniye xizmatlarining rivojlanishi ko'rib chiqiladi. Raqamli televideniening axborot uzatish sohasiga kirib borish jarayonlari, uning rivojlanishi, shuningdek, boshqa tizimlarga nisbatan afzalliklari va kamchiliklari tavsiflanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli texnologiyalar, raqamli televideniye, televidenie eshittirish, radio spektri, interaktiv xizmatlar, raqamli eshittirish.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается развитие услуг цифрового телевидения в условиях цифровизации экономики. Описаны процессы вхождения цифрового телевидения в сферу передачи информации, его развитие, а также его преимущества и недостатки по сравнению с другими системами.

Ключевые слова: цифровые технологии, цифровое телевидение, телевидение, радиоспектр, интерактивные услуги, цифровое вещание.

The expansion of digital television services in recent years has become one of the most promising and profitable areas of the national economy. Today, developed and developing countries are challenging themselves to accelerate the delivery of digital television services to impact quality of life and economic growth.

The development of digital technologies in the broadcasting industry is increasing the profitability of the communications industry and broadcasters. Therefore, issues of the economic use of digital television, improving image and sound quality are becoming relevant for the country's economy. The method of converting analogue signals into digital signals with high image quality, proposed in the early 90s, gave a huge impetus to the development of digital television broadcasting systems, and in each of the three areas listed above there has been a steady trend towards the transition to digital transmission methods.

Digital television is "multi-channel, multi-variant delivery and multimedia. This is a very complex information environment" [1]. Digital television can significantly improve the image quality on TV screens and increase the number of channels with the same broadcasting power.

Modern television broadcasting systems are developing in three directions:

- the first direction is the increase in the number of individual installations of satellite television broadcasting (radio lines are involved);
- the second direction is the introduction of broadband cable television networks capable of providing viewers with up to 100 or more TV programs (fiber-optic cable lines);
- the third direction is the introduction and development of terrestrial television in the implementation of multi-channel microwave systems (copper cable lines).

Digital television is a new stage in the development of electronic media and the use of methods and means of digital television provides a number of advantages compared to methods of transmitting information via analogue television, namely:

- increasing the noise immunity of transmission and recording paths of television signals;
- reducing the power of television broadcast transmitters;
- a significant increase in the number of television programs transmitted in one frequency range;
- improving the quality of image and sound in television receivers;
- expanding the functionality of studio equipment used in the preparation and conduct of television programs;
- transmission of various additional information in a television signal, turning a television receiver into a multifunctional information system;
- creation of interactive television systems, when using which the viewer has the opportunity to influence the transmitted program ^[2].

There is a lot in favor of digital television, but what is better - a computer-TV or just a TV - is up to the consumer to decide.

A modern multimedia TV has sound and image quality that is much higher than that of television receivers. But the cost of a TV is much less than a "multi-computer". And the mass consumer prefers the TV, especially since many different set-top boxes have appeared that allow a regular TV receiver to perform some of the functions of a personal computer.

The first mention of the possibility of digital transmission of television signals appeared in 1990.

Let us once again outline the main advantages of transmitting television information in digital form compared to analogue methods:

- transition from many television standards (there are more than 40, including NTSC, PAL, SECAM) to a single digital standard. A group of experts from a number of countries in Europe and the USA has developed a standard for digital equipment DVB - Digital Video Broadcasting,
- transmission of high-quality video images, as well as, based on digital systems, launching high-definition television, multi-program and stereoscopic television, multimedia, holographic television,
- implementation of interactive communication, when a television screen that has the functions of a computer monitor allows you to select information resources simultaneously present on it in real time,
- with a constant transmitter power of the relay satellite, a decrease in the speed of information transmission in the channel and a decrease in the probability of its failure,
- a larger number of television programs are transmitted in the repeater trunk band.

Let's consider the factors that determine the development strategy of digital television in any country. These factors, according to the author, are:

- firstly, broadcasters and producers of television programs,
- secondly, transmission companies, which must have equipment suitable for transmitting television programs in digital format,
- thirdly, the level of industrial development (does this country have the necessary potential for the production of set-top boxes and IDTV digital televisions, or will it import equipment),
- fourthly, consumers who, based on their financial situation and desires, are ready or not ready to purchase equipment for receiving digital television programs. The timing of the transition of broadcast TV from analogue to digital signal transmission depends on how quickly the population will have such televisions.
- fifthly, competitors, and they are cable television systems and direct satellite broadcast systems. Note that the interaction of satellite and cable networks with digital broadcasters will make it possible to reach a large audience and attract local advertisers, which is certainly beneficial for television networks,
- finally, sixthly, the government and its interest in implementing modern technical policy and regulating broadcaster monopolies.

Therefore, each country needs to create business models that would make the transition to new technologies practically feasible. Since the digital transition affects a number of industries, politics, economics and finance, different business models are needed for different countries, for example, industrialized and developing countries.

Currently, the tasks of digital television can be defined as follows:

- global standardization of technical means in the form of a series of international standards covering the production, distribution and demonstration of digital television,
- comprehensive solution of technical, technological and economic problems at the state level,
- research into the influence of new equipment and technology on the creative process of creating programs, assessment of new visual capabilities of digital technologies,
- research on the effectiveness of digital television in terms of a good source of income. There is no doubt that displaying advertising on such television can bring good profits, and certain audience groups are willing to pay to watch the programs they like. This requires an encryption and conditional access system that would not allow programs to be received until the viewer pays for them.

The next stage of our research will be to determine the consequences that the implementation of the digital broadcasting plan may lead to.

1. The audience is segmented by interests and by the ability to watch certain programs, therefore it is necessary to limit the rise in prices for the use of digital television channels, as well as support for cultural and sports channels at the state or sponsorship level.
2. The economy of the media will change, and processes of concentration and consolidation of corporations will find their place. On the one hand, it becomes easier for the companies included in the association to maintain profitability by creating a high-quality software product, but on the other hand, there is a danger of "standardization" of the approach leading to the formation of stereotyped values among the consumer.
3. Channels will be divided according to content and focus, taking into account viewer interests and their own capabilities; it is likely that many entertainment and music channels will appear that do not differ in the quality of information presented.

Another direction in the use of digital technology, characteristic of the first stage of the development of digital television, is the introduction of digital blocks into television receivers in order to improve image quality or expand functionality. Examples of such blocks include digital filters for separating luminance and color difference signals, reducing the influence of noise on the image, and suppressing echo signals. Devices for implementing the "freeze frame" and "frame in frame" functions, decoding and displaying additional information transmitted via the Teletext system, etc. are also widely known.

The second stage in the development of digital television is the creation of hybrid analogue-digital television systems with parameters that differ from those accepted in conventional television standards. Two main directions of changes in the television standard can be distinguished: the transition from simultaneous transmission of luminance and color-difference signals to their sequential transmission and an increase in the number of lines per frame and image elements per line. Examples of hybrid television systems are the Japanese MUSE high-definition television system and Western European systems of the MAC family.

The third stage in the development of digital television can be considered the creation of completely digital television systems.

The first proposals for fully digital television systems appeared in 1990 in Europe. These projects were based on advances in methods and techniques for efficient image encoding and compression. In May 1993, four groups of companies and research organizations representing essentially similar projects united into the "Grande Alliance" and subsequently presented a single project.

The results of all studies conducted from 1990 to 2007 were reflected in several standards. Let us indicate the most important of them.

The JPEG standard is widely used to compress still images.

Methods for compressing moving images and audio signals are described in the MPEG-1 and MPEG-2 standards. Currently, digital television systems based on television signal compression according to the MPEG-2 standard are rapidly spreading in many countries. In this case, first of all, the problem of significantly increasing the number of transmitted television programs of regular expansion is solved, since this gives a quick commercial effect.

In Europe, already in 1993, the DVB (Digital Video Broadcasting) project was adopted, in which more than 130 companies and research organizations from different countries took part. In developed countries, the question of ending analogue television broadcasting in the first decade of the 21st century has been raised.

Let's consider the method of data transmission in a standard digital television system from the technical side.

First, note that a digital signal is a discrete signal ^[3], represented in the form of values sampled at individual points in time. Secondly, this is a quantum signal ^[4]. And third, a digital signal in its final form is a symbolic representation of discrete time, quantum values.

A digital television signal is obtained from an analog television signal by converting it into digital form. This transformation includes the following three operations ^[5].

1. Discretization in time, i.e. replacing a continuous analog signal with a sequence of time-separate samples of this signal.
2. Quantization by level, which consists in rounding the value of each sample to the nearest quantization level. The fixed levels to which the samples are linked are called quantization levels.

A sampled and quantum signal is already digital.

3. To increase the noise immunity of the signal, it is better to convert it into binary form, in which case the number will be converted into a code combination of characters 0 or 1 (pulse code modulation). As a result of encoding (digitization), the sample value is represented as a number corresponding to the number of the resulting quantization level.

All three operations are performed in one unit - an analog-to-digital converter. The reverse conversion of the digital signal to analog is done in a device called a digital-to-analog converter.

As we have already said, digital information is transmitted as a sequence of binary symbols - ones and zeros. As a result of noise and interference, individual binary symbols may be received with error.

Digital channels are less susceptible to distortion and interference than analogue channels. Analog signals can take an infinite number of forms, and even a small disturbance can distort the signal beyond recognition. With digital technology, a very low error rate plus the use of error detection and correction procedures make it possible to achieve high signal accuracy. the deterioration in quality is threshold. However, if the signal-to-noise ratio falls below a certain threshold, the quality of service can abruptly change from very good to very bad. In analog systems, quality deterioration occurs more smoothly.

Digital channels are more reliable and can be produced at lower costs than analogue channels. In addition, digital software allows for more flexible implementation than analog software.

Digital systems require the allocation of a significant portion of resources for synchronization at various levels. Analog systems are easier to synchronize.

With the same channel capacity, digital systems make it possible to transmit a larger number of programs compared to analogue television; due to the reduction of necessary adjustment operations at the production stage, they are more technologically advanced; higher operational reliability of digital equipment.

Digital methods will make it possible to include television in a unified world information system through interactive television channels, as well as realize the ability to receive television programs via an Internet connection.

Two types of digital television systems can be imagined. In the first type of system, which is completely digital, information is transmitted in digital form in all links of the image transmission path. However, at present, such converters do not yet exist, so for now, digital TV systems of the second type are used, in which an analog TV signal is received from the sensor, then it is converted into digital form, processed, and then converted back into analog form.

There is a slow transformation of home computers into some kind of television. Most personal computers have begun to be equipped with a tuner card that allows them to receive digital television broadcasts. There is a convergence of two directions, and a new household device combines the advantages of both a TV and a computer.

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